

Short-Term Clinico-Functional Outcomes of Open Reduction with Endobutton Fixation for Unstable Lateral End of Clavicle Fractures

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Abstract

Fractures occurring on the distal side of the clavicle that are completely displaced have a significant likelihood of not healing properly and are linked to unfavorable functional results when treated without surgery. There are different methods to treat these fractures, but initial studies have demonstrated positive early functional results and a low rate of complications with open reduction using endobutton fixation. The aim of this research is to evaluate the surgical and postoperative clinical and functional outcomes of open reduction with endobutton fixation for patients with unstable fractures at the lateral end of the clavicle. This prospective interventional study was done in the department of orthopedics. Both male and female patients 15 to 60 years old with acromioclavicular joint disruption and acute unstable lateral end of clavicle fractures were included. They were treated with open reduction and endobutton fixation. They were followed up for 6 months using DASH and quick DASH scores. The mean (SD) age of patients was 40.77 (11.5). There were 22 (73.3%) males and 8 (26.67%) females. 7 (23.33%) patients had history of diabetes and 6 (20%) patients had history of hypertension. Mean (SD) preoperative DASH score was 59.63(5.69) and quick DASH score was 60.2 (3.27). There was significant reduction in the postoperative DASH and quick DASH score compared to pre operative values. There was no complications. Endobutton Technique done for unstable Lateral end of Cavicle Fractures. There is early

functional recovery of the patient, to the pre-injury level and also there are fewer instances of need for exit surgery.

Keywords: Lateral end of clavicle, Endobutton fixation, DASH score.

Introduction

Although mid-shaft fractures are more common, displaced fractures that impact the lateral part of the clavicle are generally less common but have inferior functional outcomes when treated nonoperatively and are more likely to result in nonunion. Therefore, it is typically recommended for patients who are in good health to undergo surgical intervention [1].

When not surgically repaired, the majority of lateral clavicle fractures tend to recover with little displacement and good functional success. While complete displaced fractures are uncommon, they are more likely to fail to heal. Older patients account for the majority of displaced injuries; many of these patients have minimal operational requirements and may respond well to nonoperative care. Patients under the age of 40 have a lower success rate with non-invasive methods of treatment [2].

Shoulder weakness, inability to move freely, and chronic pain could result from a fracture that doesn't heal. Restoration of a preexisting nonunion can be extremely challenging, thus surgery is often the first line of treatment. The most common surgical procedures for these types of injuries include coracoclavicular screws, hooked plates, as well as in recent years, lateral clavicular plates that are custom-made [3].

While primary surgical treatment has the potential to lessen the likelihood of postoperative nonunion, it is not without its risks, such as infection as well as failure of the equipment. Also, the shoulder may be less mobile after getting one of these implants because of how stiff they are, which can limit acromioclavicular mobility. As a result, after the fracture has healed, the

majority of authors advise routinely removing the implants [4]. Acromioclavicular divisions have been treated using less stiff coracoclavicular loops as well as slings made of synthetic components, allograft, including autograft. It is usually not necessary to remove the implant later on. Management of displaced lateral clavicular fractures using these methods, however, is not as clearly established [5]. The purpose of this research is to assess the surgical and postoperative clinical and functional outcomes of open reduction with endobutton fixation for patients suffering from unstable lateral end of clavicle fractures.

Materials and Methods

Study Design and Participants

Research for this prospective interventional study was carried out in the orthopedics department of a private, educational tertiary care hospital from November 2023 to May 2024. The institutional ethical committee gave their approval to the study protocol. (Ref No: 1136/ TSRMMCH&RC/ME-1/2023-IEC No.:149, Dated: 26.10.2023). The study included both male and female patients, ranging in age from fifteen to sixty years. The Acromio-clavicular joint disruption and acute unstable lateral end of clavicle fractures are the subjects that will be examined in this study. Participants did not qualify for the study if they were less than 15 or older than 60 years old, or if they had any other type of clavicle fracture, including those at the medial, shaft, or stable lateral ends.

Recruitment

30 patients coming to the out-patient department with acromio-clavicular joint disruption and acute unstable lateral end of clavicle fractures, and those satisfying the inclusion criteria were recruited. Every single patient gave their signed, informed consent.

Intervention

A comprehensive preoperative evaluation was conducted, and any concurrent medical conditions were managed by specialized medical professionals. An intravenous antibiotic with a broad spectrum of activity (Ceftriaxone and Sulbactam 1.5gm) was given to the patient one hour before the surgery and was continued for 48 hours after the surgery. The anaesthetic pain management team administered a localized block at the operated site to alleviate pain. If considered required, Non-Steroidal Anti-Inflammatory Drug (NSAID) injections and Tramadol injections were administered upon request, specifically as an intra-muscular injection. All surgeries in the study were done by the investigating team members alone.

Surgical Procedure

Under general anesthesia, the patients were all placed in the beach chair position during the procedures. A 1:200,000 adrenaline mixture was injected into the skin opening to stop the bleeding. A vertical cut measuring 6 cm was created with the base of the incision centered on the edge of the coracoid process. A vertical cut was made in the deltotrapezius fascia, then the fracture was exposed by acute dissection along the clavicle.

In order to access the location of the fracture, a 4.5 millimeters cannulated drilling was used to create bone burrows 15 mm medially to the clavicle as well as 20 mm along the coracoid. In order to minimize the possibility of atypical tunnel position, the bottom tunnel was formed under direct view by slicing the deltoid muscle at the lower side of the incision. The coracoid's flat superior wall was bored at an angle between 30° to 45° toward the coronal plane to create this tunnel. It is necessary to thread the implant's

lower button between the clavicle and coracoid before toggling it on the underside of the coracoid. Next, the suture is tightened while the fracture is being minimized under direct vision. For four weeks following surgery, the patient's arm was immobilized in a sling. Patients continued with physiotherapy until they could move their shoulders freely again.

Outcomes and Measures

The study had a follow up period of 6 months. Check X-rays were done during each visit. The DASH and Quick DASH Scores were employed to assess the functional outcomes during the follow-up period.

Statistical Analysis

The data will be properly tabulated in an MS Excel sheet and analyzed using the SPSS-19 software suite. Statistical significance is defined as a P-value less than 0.05.

Results

Demographic Characteristics

The mean (SD) age of patients with unstable lateral end of clavicle fractures was 40.77 (11.5). There were 22 (73.3%) males and 8 (26.67%) females. 7 (23.33%) patients had history of diabetes and 6 (20%) patients had history of hypertension. The demographic features of the patients are presented in table 1.

DASH score

Mean (SD) preoperative DASH score was 59.63(5.69). It was 52.43 (5.69) in 2 weeks after surgery, 42.37 (6.22) 6 weeks after surgery, 10.4 (2.37) 3 months after surgery and 2.5 (1.04) 6 months after surgery. There was significant reduction in the postoperative DASH score compared to pre operative values ($p < 0.0001$). The DASH scores are tabulated in table 2.

Quick DASH score

Mean (SD) preop quick DASH score was 60.2 (3.27). It was 51.83 (5.47) in 2 weeks after surgery, 43 (7.35) 6 weeks after surgery, 11 (2.12) 3 months after surgery and 2.47 (0.97) 6 months after surgery. There was significant reduction in the postoperative quick DASH score compared to pre operative values ($p < 0.0001$). The quick DASH scores are tabulated in table 2.

S No	Characteristic	Value
1	Age (mean $\pm$ SD)	40.77 $\pm$ 11.5
2	Sex (M:F)	22:8
3	Diabetes Mellitus	7 (23.33%)
4	Systemic hypertension	6 (20%)
5	No. of days after injury (mean $\pm$ SD)	8.23 $\pm$ 4.44
6	Duration of surgery (mins) (mean $\pm$ SD)	48.8 $\pm$ 12.72
7	Blood loss (ml) (mean $\pm$ SD)	88.33 $\pm$ 19.49

Table 1. Demographic characteristic of study population (N=30).

Score	Treatment	Mean	SD	95% CI		P value
				Lower bound ($\alpha=2.5\%$)	Upper bound ($\alpha=97.5\%$)	
DASH	Pre op	59.63	3.34	58.44	60.83	
	2 weeks	52.43	5.69	50.40	54.47	<0.0001
	6 weeks	42.37	6.22	40.14	44.59	<0.0001
	3 months	10.40	2.37	9.55	11.25	<0.0001
	6 months	2.50	1.04	2.13	2.87	<0.0001
Quick DASH	Pre op	60.20	3.27	59.03	61.37	
	2 weeks	51.83	5.47	49.88	53.79	<0.0001
	6 weeks	43.00	7.35	40.37	45.63	<0.0001
	3 months	11.00	2.12	10.24	11.76	<0.0001
	6 months	2.47	0.97	2.12	2.81	<0.0001

Table 2. DASH and quick DASH score of the study population (N=30).

Figure 1. DASH and quick DASH scores among the study population (N=30).

Figure 2. Pre-op and Post-op Xrays of a 45 year old female with unstable lateral end of clavicle fracture treated by ORIF with endobutton fixation

Figure 3. Excellent outcome post-surgery of the patient in fig 2.

Figure 4. Pre-op and Post op xrays of a 49 year old male with unstable lateral end of clavicle fracture treated by ORIF with endobutton fixation

Figure 5. Excellent outcome post surgery of the patient in fig 4.

Discussion

Our study found that individuals with single displaced lateral clavicle fractures treated with an open reduction and endobutton fixation had a low risk of sequelae and an excellent chance of bone union. Within the first half a year following their accident, the majority of patients were able to go back to their pre-injury activities and resume close to normal variety of motion as well as shoulder functioning. The elimination of the necessity for additional surgery for

removing the implant following fracture union is a significant benefit of this approach.

Direct osteosynthesis was the surgical treatment of choice for unstable distal clavicle fractures in the past [6]. There was a high incidence of hardware-related problems in the early methods that used transacromial Kirschner wires. Arthritis developed in the AC joint after surgery due to transarticular fixation using pins that crossed over the joint [7]. Subsequently, the hook plate replaced the Kirschner wire fixation [8]. Union rates were comparable between the two methods (88% for hook plate and 91% for standard Kirschner wire fixation), but complications were much lower with the hook plate (6% vs. 55%), according to a prior study. Success rates for unions ranged from 95% to 100% in subsequent research, which also revealed complication rates between 8% and 18%. Hook plates are associated with painful subacromial impingement, which 68% of patients have reported. Furthermore, because implant migration is prevalent, the majority of writers advise routinely removing the hook plate from all patients once the healing of the fracture is proven [9].

Some have proposed an alternative to the hook plate—direct osteosynthesis within the distal clavicle utilizing a locking distal radius plate [10]. Without causing trauma on the AC joint as well as acromion, specialized plates that enable several locking screws to be inserted into the tiny distal clavicle fragment demonstrate outstanding union rates [11]. Plate removal is necessary in 40% – 53% of instances, thus even with these great results, more surgery is still necessary. Moreover, not every situation will be amenable to this method [12].

In patients, functional limitation may result from unstable injuries like dislocated clavicle ending fractures, which are often accompanied by nonunion [13]. Whenever the coracoclavicular ligaments are also ruptured, the result is a possible twofold breakage within the superior shoulder suspensory complex, in

addition to the fracture [14]. This is why some researchers have pushed for alternatives to the coracoclavicular loop with sling that use artificial ligaments, allografts, or autografts to repair the ligaments. Nevertheless, it is not uncommon for these ligaments to be either partially or completely intact, with the bulk of the ligament complex still linked to the lateral fragment, a third inferior fragment, or an incomplete disruption (Neer type IIB damage). For the majority of patients, primary ligamentous restoration is not required [15].

The endobutton should not be used to augment the ligaments, but rather as a "fixation device" to keep the fracture from worsening while it heals. The arthroscopic insertion of a comparable endobutton device and minimally invasive closure reduction have been detailed [16]. Because of the complicated arrangement of inferior displacement of the shoulder girdle together with retraction with the diaphyseal fragment—often with "button-hole" of the deltotrapezius fascia—obtaining an adequate reduction of two-part fractures can be challenging [17].

Another common issue is the periosteum infolding around the fracture site, which can initially make precise reduction impossible. A precise reduction is easier to achieve under straight vision, and operative fluoroscopic images are frequently deceiving [18]. Along with its relatively narrow breadth of 14.2 mm (ranging from 11 to 19 in 102 scapulae), the superior coracoid pillar also has a smooth top surface that is angled 45° medially in the coronal plane. Even with the use of a jig, arthroscopic procedures may still have trouble accurately placing a bone tunnel centrally inside the coracoid [19].

The possibility of implant cut-out and failure is elevated when an eccentric tube is placed [20]. For accurate center placement inside the pillar, it is best to begin drilling the coracoid tunnel while looking directly at it [21]. From a cosmetic standpoint, there is little difference between the conventional

surgical approach and the arthroscopic procedure, and the dimensions of the incisions for both methods is almost identical [22].

The limitations of our study are the small sample size and lack of long term follow-up. Results about alternative treatment methods cannot be stated with certainty due to the lack of a control group and comparison arms. Results at long-term follow-up are still unknown, although all cases achieved midterm follow-up.

Conclusion

By using the Endobutton Technique for unstable Lateral end of Clavicle Fractures, there is early functional recovery of the patient, to the pre-injury level and also there are fewer instances of need for exit surgery. Based on their expertise, training, and equipment, surgeons should choose the best procedure. Reducing intraoperative injury is another major issue for orthopedists, along with fracture repair, as minimally invasive methods like arthroscopy have grown more prominent in traumatic orthopedics.

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